

Photoinduced electron transfer reaction of 2-mercaptobenzothiazole and methylene blue : Mechanism and kinetics

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Abstract : 2-Mercaptobenzothiazole (2MBT) is a more toxic as compare to the benzothiazole (BT) and the photosensitized reaction of 2MBT with methylene blue (MB) in the alkaline medium using visible light has been studied to convert 2MBT to less toxic benzothiazole. 2MBT shows the λ_{\max} at 230 nm and at 320 nm between the pH range 2–6 and the λ_{\max} at 235 nm and at 315 nm in the pH range 8–12. 2MBT exists as thione and thiol form in equilibrium. The irradiation of MB molecule with visible light excites it to singlet excited state which gives triplet excited state on ISC which interacts with 2MBT anion and transfer it's energy to 2MBT anion and comes back to ground state (dipole-dipole energy transfer mechanism). The triplet excited state of 2MBT anion gives benzothiazole radical and sulphur radical anion. The benzothiazole radical will abstract hydrogen from a hydrogen donor to form benzothiazole. The sulphur radical anion will react with a proton to form a SH^o radical. As the reaction precedes the thiol form is converted to anion form. The apparent rate of the reaction has been calculated and the effect of pH, concentration of the sensitizer, the light intensity on the apparent rate of the reaction has been studied. The quantum efficiency of the photochemical reaction is calculated using potassium ferri oxalate actinometer and the effect of the concentration of the substrate on the quantum efficiency is calculated. The reaction mechanism and the excited states involved have been suggested.

Keywords : 2-Mercaptobenzothiazole, photosensitizer reaction, exciplex formation, singlet oxygen, dipole-dipole energy transfer mechanism.

Introduction

Nowadays many toxic organic compounds from different sources are discharged into the water bodies and the problems of water quality have become more important that the quality of water. These chemicals are not easily removed during waste water treatment. The classical biological oxidation methods failed to eliminate such micro pollutants to the desired level where as physiochemical technique just transferred them from one phase to another without destroying them. Such classical biological oxidation methods and physiochemical techniques are useful only for the high level concentrations of pollutants, but when the pollutants are present in a very trace level such methods have failed to remove these pollutants from water bodies. Photochemical degradation is an important technique to convert this toxic compound into non-toxic material^{1,2} at a very trace level.

2-Mercaptobenzothiazole (2MBT) is an important member of benzothiazole (BT) group, constituted from a

benzene ring fused with a thiazole ring. 2MBT is an important industrial chemical with an annual production of approximately 40,000 tons in Europe. It has been used for the vulcanization of rubber and as a basic accelerator in ethylene-propylene-diene rubbers. 2MBT and its derivatives are also good stabilizers which are used in the plastic manufacturing. 2MBT has been used in the manufacturing of many rubber products such as tennis shoes, elastic underwear, rubber footwear, gloves, tyres and many other products. 2MBT used as an intermediate in the production of many compounds and are also used as fungicide, herbicide and bactericide in agriculture, some of which may decompose and form water soluble 2MBT and thus generally found in the aquatic medium and can easily enters to food cycle.

Due to it's multipurpose use, 2MBT derivatives are frequently detected in both waste water treatment plant and surface water and can come into contact with potable water. Several epidemiologic studies have reported that

workers in the rubber industry have an increased risk of cancer³⁻⁷. The studies suggest that rats chronically exposed to 2MBT show increase in various type of tumors, such as adrenal gland, pituitary gland, liver and renal pelvis tumors. The laboratory and epidemiological studies suggest that 2MBT acts as a carcinogen in mammals⁸. De Wever *et al.* have reported that 2MBT has toxic effects on many bacteria, and its presence inhibits biodegradation of other compounds⁹. Its toxicity towards microorganisms¹⁰⁻¹³ and its allergenicity resulting in serious dermatomes¹⁴ and its potential mutagenic effects¹⁵, make its presence in the environment a matter of great concern and thus it becomes important to study the photochemical activity of 2MBT.

The present study reports the photochemical reaction of 2MBT using the cationic dye, methylene blue as photosensitizer in the aqueous alkaline medium on irradiation with visible light. The cationic dye, methylene blue has been used as photosensitizer. The effects of the pH, the concentration of the sensitizer, the concentration of the substrate and the light intensity have been evaluated on the apparent rate of the reaction. The reaction has been used to determine the quantum efficiency and to determine whether the reaction is monophotonic or biphotonic. The effect of the oxygen and the free radical scavenger on the reaction has been studied. The mechanism of the photosensitized reaction has been suggested. Methylene blue has been used as a photosensitizer in the present study which has been used as sensitizer in a number of photochemical reactions¹⁶⁻¹⁹.

Results and discussion

Spectral characteristics :

Li *et al.*²⁰ have reported the UV-Visible absorption spectra of 2MBT obtained from the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) Library. Experiment shows that the 2MBT ($4 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$) exhibits two well-defined maxima one at 230 nm ($\epsilon = 11500 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and second at 320 nm ($\epsilon = 19580 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) between the pH range 2-6. The maxima at 235 nm ($\epsilon = 15800 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and at 315 nm ($\epsilon = 11940 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) are observed in the pH range 8-12.

According to the FTIR and Raman spectra of 2MBT, the thiol form of 2MBT is more stable than the thione form of 2MBT and dimeric conformation is more stable

than monomeric conformation²¹. Thione and thiol tautomeric forms (Fig. 1) of 2MBT are in equilibrium in the pH range 2-12, which shows a marginal change in molar absorptivity with change in the pH of the solution. 2MBT

Fig. 1. Thiol and thione tautomeric forms of 2MBT.

is inaccessible at acidic pH due to the presence of thione and thiol form containing “SH” and “NH” group respectively, however, it has been demonstrated that a pH greater than 8 result in a structural transition from the neutral to basic form. The thiol form can interact with OH^- and forms an anion in the alkaline solution. The spectral changes are reversible depending on the pH of the solution.

2MBT is highly resistant to biodegradation²². Direct photolysis of 2-mercaptobenzothiazole disulfide gave 2-mercaptobenzothiazole and 2-thiocyanatobenzothiazole in acetonitrile²³. Hansoon *et al.*²⁴ have reported the stability of 2MBT in the buffer solution at pH 6.5. However in the present study 2MBT was found to be photo stable in acidic as well as in the alkaline medium, when irradiated by visible light. It was also found during the experiment that 2MBT and MB don't interact in the ground state but when the reaction mixture containing 2MBT ($4 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$) and MB ($1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$) maintained at different pH between 2 to 12 were exposed to the visible radiation and the spectra were recorded against the reagent blank, the reaction mixture does not show any significant change in the pH range 2-6 but it undergoes photoreaction in the pH range of 8-12.

The changes of the absorption spectrum were plotted against time which show decrease at the λ_{max} 235 nm and 310 nm (Fig. 2) and shows increase in the absorbance at 215 nm and 260 nm with time and an isosbestic point was observed at 225 nm, however in the region of 245 nm to 265 nm, there are no isosbestic points and this indicates that the reaction does not consist just in the transformation of one species to another.

Determination of the apparent rate constant and effect of different parameters on apparent rate constant :

The reaction follows the first-order reaction kinetics

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra ((a) at T_0 , (b) at T_{80} , (c) at T_{160} , (d) at T_{240}) of the photosensitized reaction of 2MBT with MB, 2MBT : 4×10^{-5} mol L^{-1} , MB : 1×10^{-5} mol L^{-1} , time interval : 80 min, 100 W tungsten lamp, pH 11.

as the plot of $2 + \log OD$ (optical density) vs time (at 315 nm) is a straight line with a positive slope (Fig. 3). The rate constant (apparent k value) has been determined by the expression :

$$\text{Rate constant} = 2.303 \times \text{slope}$$

The half life of the reaction has been observed at different concentration of the substrate and $t_{1/2}$ value is constant over the above range of the substrate concentration. This suggests that the photochemical reaction is of the first order in 2MBT.

Fig. 3. $[2 + \log OD]$ vs time plot of the photosensitized reaction of 2MBT with MB on exposure at 310 nm, 2MBT : 4×10^{-5} mol L^{-1} , MB : 1×10^{-5} mol L^{-1} , time interval : 15 min, 100 W tungsten lamp, pH 11.

Effect of the pH :

Wang *et al.*²⁵ have reported the significance of the pH of the solution on the photo catalytic degradation of 2MBT

using Fe_2O_3 /oxalate system under UVA light irradiation. In this investigation, the effect of the pH value on the 2MBT photo degradation with MB in aqueous medium was studied in the pH interval range from 2 to 12. Fig. 4 showed the dependence of apparent k value for 2MBT degradation on the pH in the presence of 1×10^{-5} mol L^{-1} MB, under 15×10^8 E/s visible light intensity.

Fig. 4. Effect of the pH on the apparent rate of the reaction measured at 310 nm, 2MBT : 4×10^{-5} mol L^{-1} , MB : 1×10^{-5} mol L^{-1} , time interval: 10 min, 100 W tungsten lamp, pH 11.

The spectrum of 2MBT was recorded at several pH values ranging from 2 to 12, while keeping the concentration of 2MBT as constant. The absorbance at λ_{max} 315 nm was plotted against the pH of the solution. The centre of the sigmoidal curve gave the pK_a value of 7.69 ± 0.05 as reported²⁶. At different pH value, the total concentration of 2MBT was shared between thione and thiol forms, which have different reactivity with respect to OH. Increase of the pH would result in an increase of the thiol anion, and hence increase the apparent rate of the reaction.

In the pH range 2 to 6, 2MBT is present in equilibrium as thione and thiol species containing “NH” and “SH” group respectively, which don’t reacts with excited MB cation and doesn’t show photo reaction in the acidic medium. Thiol group is the critical functional group of 2MBT²⁷ which forms the anion “S⁻” in the alkaline medium due to the removal of H atom, which can be observed by decreases in molar absorptivity at 320 nm in the alkaline medium as compared to the acidic medium. The thione species containing “NH” is alkaline and remains the same in the alkaline medium while the thiol species containing “SH” is acidic which forms anion “S⁻”

in the alkaline medium and reacts with cationic dye MB to give the reaction.

The spectrum (Fig. 2) shows decrease in the absorbance at the λ_{\max} of both thione and thiol species which remain in equilibrium. The absorbance at the λ_{\max} 315 nm ($k = 6.48 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ at 315 nm) decreases faster than absorbance at λ_{\max} 235 nm ($k = 3.21 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ at 235 nm). The absorbance decreases at 315 nm is due to the photo degradation reaction of 2MBT to form benzothiazole, while the absorbance decrease at 235 nm is due to the conversion of thione to thiol tautomeric form to maintain the equilibrium. As the reaction proceeds the concentration of the anionic species of the 2MBT thiol form decreases. The thione-thiol equilibrium shifts to right side and the thione form converts to the thiol form to maintain the equilibrium.

Effect of the initial concentration of sensitizer :

Fig. 5 showed the dependence of 2MBT photo degradation on the initial concentration of sensitizer under $15 \times 10^8 \text{ E/s}$ visible light irradiation. Fig showed the dependence of the apparent k value (k) on the sensitizer

Fig. 5. Effect of the sensitizer concentration on the apparent rate of the reaction at 310 nm, 2MBT : $4 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$, MB : $4 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ to $2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$, time interval : 10 min, 100 W tungsten lamp, pH 11.

concentration. The results showed that the photo degradation of 2MBT did not occur in the absence of MB. However, 2MBT degradation could be efficiently enhanced in the presence of MB. 2MBT has its λ_{\max} below 400 nm and is not photodegraded directly by the visible light. Methylene blue absorbs visible radiation at 665 nm and gets excited, which on collision with the 2MBT, transfers energy to it. The first-order apparent kinetic constant (k) for 2MBT degradation increased with increasing sensi-

tizer concentration then becomes constant with increasing sensitizer concentration. However, the first-order kinetic constant for 2MBT degradation decreased as the MB concentration reached above a threshold level where the self deactivation of the sensitizer molecule takes place by intermolecular collision²⁸. Therefore, the optimal sensitizer concentration value was $1.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ which mostly favoured the photo degradation of 2MBT in the experimental condition.

Effect of the initial concentration of substrate :

The first-order apparent kinetic constant k remains the same $5.07 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$ with increasing substrate concentration from $2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ to $6 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ and decreases slightly at the higher concentration of substrate. This indicates that the substrate concentration value ranges from $2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ to $6 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ gives the best result for 2MBT degradation. $4 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ substrate concentration value is selected for further reaction. The first-order apparent kinetic constants k remaining constant in the concentration range shows that the reaction is independent of the initial concentration of the substrate²⁹.

Study in aerobic and anaerobic conditions to check a possible involvement of singlet oxygen :

Fiehn *et al.*³⁰ reported that the ozonation intermediates of 2MBT include benzothiazole, 2-hydroxybenzothiazole and benzothiazole-2-sulfite. Chipinda *et al.*²⁷ have also observed the oxidation transformation of 2MBT in latex gloves to the disulfide 2,2'-dithiobis (benzothiazole) when hypochlorous acid, iodine and hydrogen peroxide were used as oxidants. Therefore the reaction was studied in the anaerobic condition to observe the participation of singlet oxygen during the photosensitized reaction.

The cationic dye methylene blue – photo sensitizer – absorbs the visible radiation and goes to the singlet excited state and is converted to the triplet state by intersystem crossing (ISC). The excitation energy of the sensitizer molecule is transferred to $^3\text{O}_2$ molecule and converts it to the singlet state, while photo sensitizer molecule returns to the ground state. This singlet oxygen is a highly reactive species which gives the photo oxygenation reaction. Methylene blue is reportedly efficient sensitizers for the conversion of triplet oxygen to singlet oxygen in the presence of light^{31–35}. The first-order ap-

parent kinetic constant was calculated for the exposed solutions of the different concentration of the substrate [2MBT] and the sensitizer MB in the aerobic as well as in the anaerobic condition. The first-order apparent kinetic constant in the anaerobic condition $4.61 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ and $18.42 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ at 235 nm and 315 nm respectively, does not show change and remains the same ($4.61 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ and $18.42 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ at 235 nm and 315 nm respectively) as in the aerobic condition. The ϕ value of the reaction was also calculated in the anaerobic condition of the reaction which remains constant and same as in the aerobic condition. However the experimental result suggests that the singlet oxygen does not participate in the photosensitized reaction of 2MBT.

Effect of the free radical scavenger :

The effect of the free radical scavenger on the photosensitized reaction of 2MBT was studied by changing the medium from aqueous alkaline to methanolic alkaline. The solutions of the different concentration of substrate [2MBT] and the sensitizer MB were prepared in the alkaline methanolic solution and irradiated with the visible light. The two species of 2MBT thiol and thione show λ_{max} at 230 nm and at 315 nm in the alkaline methanolic solution. The first-order apparent kinetic constant for the 2MBT degradation reaction in the aqueous alkaline medium was $4.13 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ and $18.42 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ at 235 nm and 315 nm respectively changed drastically to $1.84 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ and $3.83 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ at 235 nm and 315 nm respectively in the alkaline methanolic solvent. The photochemical reaction shows sharp decrease in the alkaline methanolic solvent suggests that there is free radical formation during the reaction³⁶.

Effect of the light intensity :

Light intensity is another important factor to be considered during photochemical process. Generally, higher light intensity can lead to higher degradation rate for organic pollutants in photochemical reaction. The same results were obtained in this investigation as shown in Table 1. The solutions of the different concentration of the substrate [2MBT] and the sensitizer MB were prepared in the aqueous alkaline solution and irradiated with the visible light of the different intensity. The increase of the light intensity [Einstein/second (E/s)] shows positive effect and the first-order apparent rate constant of the

Table 1. Effect of the light intensity on the apparent rate of the reaction and on the quantum efficiency at 310 nm, 2MBT : $4 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$, MB : $1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$, time interval : 10 min, 100 W tungsten lamp, pH 11

Light intensity ($I \times 10^8$) E/s	Rate of the reaction at 310 nm ($r \times 10^{-2}$) mole/L min [$r \pm 0.5$]	Quantum efficiency
5	8.75	0.54
10	18.42	0.54
15	27.74	0.54
20	34.56	0.54
25	45.45	0.54

reaction increases as the light intensity increases. The increase in the number of the photons increases the number of the excited sensitizer molecule and the apparent rate of the reaction also increases. A linear relationship has been observed between the light intensity and the first-order apparent rate constant of the reaction.

The quantum efficiency :

The quantum efficiency of the photoreaction of 2MBT and MB has been determined using potassium ferrioxalate actinometer under various initial concentrations of 2MBT. The plot of the ϕ value and the initial concentration of the 2MBT (Fig. 6(A)) shows a straight line with positive slope suggesting the dependence of the quantum efficiency on the initial concentration of 2MBT.

$$\Phi_{\text{Prod}} = \frac{k_2FG[2\text{-MBT}]}{k_d + k_2[2\text{-MBT}]} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{1}{\Phi_{\text{Prod}}} = \frac{1}{FG} + \frac{k_d}{k_2FG[2\text{-MBT}]} \quad (2)$$

where

$$F = \frac{k_p}{k_p + k_e} \text{ and } G = \frac{k_z}{k_{\text{isc}} + k_{\text{sd}}}$$

Eq. (2) represents the dependence of the inverse of the quantum efficiency upon the inverse of the concentration of the substrate. As the concentration of 2MBT increases, the plot of the inverse of the quantum efficiency vs inverse of the concentration of the substrate (Fig. 6(B)) shows the linearity with positive slope indicating that the electron transfer from the anion "S⁻" of 2MBT to the excited state cationic dye MB in the triplet excited state

Fig. 6. Plot of (A) quantum efficiency vs substrate concentration (B) inverse of the quantum efficiency vs inverse of the substrate concentration at 310 nm, 2MBT : 2×10^{-5} mol L⁻¹ to 8×10^{-5} mol L⁻¹, MB : 1×10^{-5} mol L⁻¹, time interval : 10 min, 100 W tungsten lamp, pH 11.

and no exciplex formation takes place during the photosensitized reaction³⁷. The photo reaction product formation is monophotonic process as the quantum efficiency does not change with increase in light intensity.

Identification of the photo product :

The reaction mixture after exposure to the visible radiation for 240 min was analyzed for the reaction product, showing the presence of organic compound. The photoproduct shows three absorbance maxima in UV spectrum at 210 nm, 265 nm and 310 nm having the molar absorptivity of 20000 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹, 5000 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 1375 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ respectively. The UV spectrum of the photoproduct compares very well with the UV spectrum of the benzothiazole solution of the same concentration in the reaction condition (Table 2).

The reaction product was isolated by extracting the exposed solution 4 times with 5 ml CH₂Cl₂. The CH₂Cl₂ was collected and evaporated to dryness and the product was dissolved in 5 ml methanol. The methanolic solution of the product was used for the GC-MS analysis. A single peak was observed in the gas chromatogram suggesting

Species present	λ_{\max} (nm)	Molar absorptivity (L mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)
Photo product	215	20000
	260	5000
	300	1375
Benzothiazole	217	18620
	251	5495
	295	1349

that there is only one photoproduct. The RT (retention time) of the reaction product matches with the RT of the standard solution of benzothiazole. Li *et al.*³⁸ compared the LC retention time and UV absorption spectra with the standard benzothiazole and confirmed that benzothiazole appeared as the initial intermediate from the 2MBT degradation and lasted for a long period during the 2MBT degradation reaction. The mass spectrum (Fig. 7) of the isolated product shows three main peaks. The peak at : m/z 136 (M+1, 100%) which is also the base peak corresponds to [m+1] + protonated molecular ion. The second and third peaks are observed at m/z 108 and m/z 91. The triplet excited state molecule of 2MBT undergoes decomposition to give benzothiazole as photoproduct. Malouki *et al.*³⁹ have found that the anionic form of 2MBT was photo converted into benzothiazole and 2-hydroxybenzothiazole when it irradiated by UV radiation in aerated medium.

Mechanism :

The 2MBT exists as thione and thiol form in equilibrium at different pH and have λ_{\max} at 235 nm and 310 nm which do not absorb visible light and are photo stable. The thiol form of 2MBT undergoes deprotonation in the alkaline medium and the anion of the thiol form is in equilibrium with thiol form.

Methylene blue (MB) has λ_{\max} at 665 nm which absorbs visible radiation and forms singlet excited molecule. The singlet excited state MB gives triplet excited state of the MB on ISC. The cationic dye methylene blue accepts electron from anion of the thiol form and transfers energy to 2MBT anion (dipole-dipole energy transfer mechanism). The 2MBT anion goes to triplet excited state and MB comes back to the ground state (Scheme 1).

Fig. 7. Mass spectra of the photoproduct of 2MBT and MB on exposure.

The product formation can take place from triplet excited state of the 2MBT by two processes. Freeman *et al.*⁴⁰ have reported that if the bond fission energy is lower than the triplet excited state then the product formation can occur directly from the triplet excited state of 2MBT. The process should be homolytic bond fission. The product formation will be by an ion pair formation if the bond fission energy is higher than the triplet state. The process should be heterolytic bond fission. The formation of the benzothiazole radical and sulphur radical anion is due to homolytic fission of C=S bond. The C=S bond fission energy is near to 138 kcal per mol which may be lower than the excited triplet state. The homolytic fission of the C=S bond of the triplet excited 2MBT anion occurs to give benzothiazole radical and sulphur radical anion. The benzothiazole radical will abstract hydrogen from a hydrogen donor to form benzothiazole. The sulphur radical anion will react with a proton to form a SH^o radical.

The higher value of the quantum efficiency for the reaction suggest that excited species undergoes decomposition more efficiently than deactivation. The thione and thiol tautomer show decrease in the absorbance with time. The concentration of 2MBT anion decreases as the reaction proceeds. The equilibrium shifts to right as reaction

precedes and the thione species is converted to thiol species to form the thiol anion.

Experimental

2MBT, methylene blue, potassium trioxalate ferrate, ammonium ferric sulphate, sodium acetate, phenanthroline, were used as received. Hydrochloric acid (HCl) and sodium hydroxide (NaOH) were analytical grade. Ethyl alcohol was HPLC grade. All chemicals were used as received. Water was doubly distilled. The solutions were kept in the dark at room temperature and were diluted as per the requirement.

100 W tungsten filament light source has been used for the exposure of the sample solution, convex lens is used to converge the irradiation and a glass water jacket is used to decrease the temperature of the solution. Light intensity is measured using "Light intensity measurement meter" (form Iwiss Solar, Model Number : TM206). All the spectral measurements have been done on UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Chemito - 2100). The pH was adjusted by addition of HCl or NaOH solutions, respectively and has been measured using pH-meter (Systronics, India) with glass calomel electrode.

The four sets of 2MBT solution (4.0×10^{-5} mol L⁻¹)

Scheme 1. Mechanism of 2MBT degradation.

in alkaline aqueous medium were prepared. Two of them contain methylene blue (MB) ($1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$) as a photosensitizer. Two flasks, each containing methylene blue (MB) and without MB were kept in dark for 24 h while remaining similar flasks were exposed to the visible light from 100 W tungsten lamp. The course of the reaction was followed by recording the spectrum of the exposed solution with a control solution in the range of

200–300 nm against reagent blank. The flask kept in the dark and the flask exposed without sensitizer did not show difference in the spectrum when compared to the control; while the exposed flask containing sensitizer showed shift in λ_{max} .

The effect of varying concentration of MB (in the range of $4 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ to $3 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$) and 2MBT (in the range of $2.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ to 8.0×10^{-5}

mol L⁻¹) on the apparent rate of the reaction has been studied respectively. The solutions were deaerated or saturated with O₂ by purging with nitrogen or O₂ respectively, for 30 min via a needle through the cap. The effect of the free radical scavenger on the photo sensitized reaction was studied by changing the medium from aqueous alkaline to methanolic alkaline. Light intensity can be varied by changing the distance of the sample solution from the tungsten lamp source, and intensity was measured using "Light intensity measurement meter". The study was carried out at room temperature and pressure. The quantum efficiency of the photo reaction has been evaluated using potassium ferri oxalate actinometer.

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